

INFLUENCE OF STRAND DISPERSION METHOD ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF RANDOMLY ORIENTED CARBON FIBER STRAND THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Randomly oriented strand composites, Mechanical properties, Scatter, Dispersion process, Monte Carlo simulation

ABSTRACT

Discontinuous carbon fiber composites with randomly oriented tapes are promising materials with both high mechanical performance and a good formability. This study investigated the influence of tape dispersion method on mechanical properties of carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT), consisting of chopped carbon fiber/thermoplastic prepreg. Tensile tests, four-point flexural tests, and three-point impact tests were performed to CTT manufactured by different tape dispersion methods: bulk molding-CTT and sheet molding-CTT. Moreover, the fracture behavior was characterized with high speed camera and optical microscope. Experimental results showed great improvement of tensile, flexural, and impact strength and decrease of scatter of mechanical properties from bulk molding CTT to sheet molding CTT. The observation of optical microscope suggested that dominant fracture mode changed from delamination of tapes' interlayer to fiber breakage, and it made the strength of sheet molding CTT greater. The results of this study are quite useful to manufacture CTT with higher strength and lower scatter of mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous carbon fiber composites with randomly oriented strands or tapes are promising materials for complex-shaped parts, especially in the aviation and automotive industries. These materials composed of long discontinuous fiber combine good mechanical properties with a good formability, and have already been applied to some commercial products, such as the window frames of the Boeing 787 Dreamliner [1], suspension control arms for the Lamborghini Sesto Elemento [2], and the rear door frame of the Toyota Prius Plug-in hybrid [3]. This type of materials has been investigated in some research groups from mechanical properties and the fracture behavior [4,5] to the behavior during molding complex-shaped products [6] and modeling techniques [7,8]. Especially in such material systems, carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT), consisting of chopped carbon fiber/thermoplastic prepreg, are expected to achieve high cycle molding of complex parts because the press machine used for metal forming can be applied to molding of thermoplastics.

CTT are made by the following process: cutting unidirectional prepreg into tapes, tape dispersion, and compression molding. Although tape geometry or size effect and molding conditions has been discussed in many previous studies, the effect of strand dispersion on mechanical properties have not been investigated sufficiently. CTT consist of several centimeters of tapes, so mechanical properties have non-negligible level of scatter in small parts. Hence in this study, the effect of tape dispersion on not only mean value but scatter of mechanical properties are investigated by three kinds of mechanical testing and observation with some instruments. The subsequent section presents the details of CTT making process with two types of tape dispersion methods and experimental procedures. After that, experimental results are shown and discussed, and we summarize the conclusions in the final part.

2 MATERIAL FABRICATION

Dispersion method of tapes was focused on in this study because it seems strongly to affect the mechanical properties of CTT. Discontinuous fiber composites with similar material system are manufactured by other research institutes using compression molding of bulkily mixed tapes. On the other hand, another method uses water or air to make a CTT prepreg sheet with well dispersed tapes, stacks the sheets, and presses them by compression molding. In this study, CTT manufactured by the former and the latter methods are called BM-CTT: bulk molding-CTT and SM-CTT: sheet molding CTT, respectively.

2.1 Unidirectional prepreg tape

Tapes were cut from unidirectional prepreg sheet, which was produced by a tow-spreading technology [9]. The carbon fiber tow was spread by the air flow and then the fiber tow was attached to both faces of a polyamide 6 film by heating. The carbon fiber and polyamide 6 were TR50S (Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd.) and Diamiron C® (Mitsubishi Plastics Co., Ltd.), respectively. The thickness of the prepreg sheet was approximately 44 μm and the volume fraction of fiber was 54%. The prepreg was chopped into pieces with 5 mm in width and 19 mm in length in this study.

2.2 BM-CTT fabrication

Required amount of tapes were just mixed bulkily and put into the molding die. The molding method was shown in Figure 1. This method has an advantage of low-cost production cycle thanks to less making process and less waste. On the other hand, a heap of tapes is bulky in the molding die and tapes are hard to be oriented in in-plane direction.

Figure 1: Fabrication of bulk molding-CTT. Bulkily mixed tapes were put into the molding die and then they were compression molded.

2.3 SM-CTT fabrication

Figure 2 indicated the diagram of SM-CTT fabrication. Tapes were put into the water and then the water was discharged from the bottom of the tank after well stirred. After that, dispersed tapes were dried and heated to attach the neighbor tape to each other in order to make a portable sheet, called CTT prepreg sheet in the figure. SM-CTT were manufactured by compression molding of stacked CTT prepreg sheets.

The appearance of fabricated CTT plate were shown in Figure 3. Tapes in the BM-CTT plate deformed, while tapes in the SM-CTT plate kept their shapes.

Figure 2: Fabrication of sheet molding-CTT using water flow. CTT prepreg sheets were made of well dispersed tapes and the sheets were stacked in the molding die, then they were compression molded.

Figure 3: The appearance of fabricated bulk molding- and sheet molding-CTT.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The dimensions of specimens and the testing condition for tensile, four-point flexural, and three-point impact tests were shown in Table 1. Tensile tests were conducted in compliance with ISO527-4 [10], using specimens with length of 250 mm, width of 35 mm, and thickness of 3.0 mm. The longitudinal strain was measured with an extensometer attached to the center of the specimen and its gauge length was set as 50 mm. A universal testing machine (Autograph AG-Xplus 250 kN, Shimadzu Corporation) was used at the stroke speed of 1.0 mm/min and the number of specimens was six.

Four-point flexural tests were conducted in compliance with ASTM D7264 [11], using specimens with length of 125 mm, width of 35 mm, and thickness of 3.1 mm. A laser displacement meter was used in order to measure the deflection in the center of the undersurface. A universal testing machine (Autograph AGS-X 5 kN, Shimadzu Corporation) was used at the stroke speed of 5.0 mm/min and the number of specimens was six. A high-speed camera was used to observe the fracture behavior.

Three-point impact tests were conducted in compliance with JIS K7084 [12], using specimens with length of 125 mm, width of 35 mm, and thickness of 3.1 mm. A hydraulic impact testing machine (HITS P-10, Shimadzu Corporation) was used at the stroke speed of 3.8 m/sec and the number of specimens was six. The fracture behavior was observed by a high-speed camera as with four-point flexural tests.

(a) Tensile test						
Specimen length [mm]	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Gauge length [mm]	Stroke speed [mm/min]	Number of specimens	
250	35	3.0	50	1.0	6	
(b) Four-point flexural test						
Specimen length [mm]	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Support span [mm]	Load span [mm]	Stroke speed [mm/min]	Number of specimens
125	35	3.1	96	48	5.0	6
(c) Three-point impact test						
Specimen length [mm]	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Support span [mm]	Stroke speed [m/sec]	Number of specimens	
125	35	3.1	96	3.8	6	

Table 1: Dimensions of specimens and testing condition for (a) tensile test, (b) four-point flexural test, and (c) three-point impact test.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Tension

The tensile moduli and strength of BM-CTT and SM-CTT were listed in Table 2 and the chart was shown in Figure 4. Regarding the mean values, although the moduli of two types of CTT were almost the same, the strength of SM-CTT was 35.7% higher than those of BM-CTT. The tensile strength was clearly improved by making CTT prepreg sheet. As sectional images in Figure 5 indicated, tapes comprising BM-CTT specimen were deformed and layers were oriented in out-of-plane direction, while most of tapes in SM-CTT were distributed in each plane parallel to the surface. In-plane tapes could withstand a higher longitudinal load than winding tapes. Therefore, it is inferred that the difference of strength between BM- and SM-CTT was caused by tape orientations.

The error bar in Figure 4 indicated the standard deviation of each property. The scatter of tensile properties of SM-CTT was smaller than that of BM-CTT. The coefficient of variation (CV), which is a proportion of the mean value and the standard deviation, of tensile modulus can be simulated by a model proposed in a previous research [13]. The model assumes that each tape is transformed to an equivalent square and it is laid without overlapping. The CV of modulus showed good agreement with the calculated result, 1.4%, in SM-CTT, but disagreement in BM-CTT. It is because well dispersed tape in SM-CTT enable to satisfy the assumption.

	Tension		Flexure		Impact	
	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]	Strength [MPa]	Absorbed energy [J]
BM-CTT	37.6 (9.4%)	384 (12.4%)	34.4 (15.5%)	403 (14.0%)	543 (23.9%)	11.6 (28.9%)
SM-CTT	41.0 (2.6%)	521 (5.8%)	40.7 (3.7%)	548 (1.5%)	739 (3.8%)	12.0 (8.0%)

(): Coefficient of variation

Table 2: Mechanical properties obtained by tensile, four-point flexural, and three-point impact tests.

Figure 4: Tensile modulus and strength by tensile tests. Error bars show the standard deviation.

Figure 5: Sectional images of bulk molding- and sheet molding-CTT.

4.2 Flexure

The flexural moduli and strength were listed in Table 2 and the chart was shown in Figure 6. Both the mean values of the flexural moduli and the strength of SM-CTT were larger than those of BM-CTT. The strength especially improved by 36.0% due to wet dispersion process. Moreover, the scatter of flexural properties of SM-CTT was much lower than of BM-CTT. The CV of flexural modulus can be predicted by a model proposed in another previous research [14]. Although the CV of experimental result showed excellent agreement with the simulated value, 3.1%, in SM-CTT, disagreement in BM-CTT as with the case of tensile modulus. The lower level of scatter and its prediction makes finite element analysis easier.

Figure 7 showed propagation of the crack during tests and the typical stress-strain curves of two types of CTT. The fracture changed ductile behavior to brittle behavior between BM- and SM-CTT. In BM-CTT, a compressive failure occurred and the initial tensile failure propagated in the oblique direction while the interlayer of tapes was being peeled. Such interlayer fracture progressed gradually, so the fracture of BM-CTT was ductile. As for SM-CTT, the strain energy had been stored before the initial tensile failure occurred, then the crack propagated immediately to the entire thickness to release the stored strain energy. It is because SM-CTT showed the brittle fracture behavior.

Figure 6: Flexural modulus and strength by four-point flexural tests. Error bars show the standard deviation.

Figure 7: Propagation of the crack and typical stress-strain curves of bulk molding- and sheet molding-CTT in four-point flexural tests.

4.3 Impact

The impact strength and the total absorbed energy were listed in Table 2 and the chart was shown in Figure 8. The scatter of impact properties of SM-CTT was much lower than those of BM-CTT, as tensile and flexural properties were. Regarding mean values, the impact strength of SM-CTT was 36.1% higher than that of BM-CTT, but the total absorbed energy was almost the same. The fracture behavior of BM-CTT can be divided into two types shown in Figure 9 (a). One was as follows: the compressive failure occurred first and subsequently the delamination propagated from the compressive failure. After that, the tensile failure occurred, the delamination propagated from tensile failure, and then it reached the final failure. The other was as follows: any compressive failure did not occur, but the tensile failure occurred early. The tensile failure propagated in the oblique direction and then it reached the final failure. In SM-CTT, on the other hand, as soon as the tensile failure occurred, it propagated to the entire thickness instantly as with the flexural failure. These characterizations mean that the fracture of BM-CTT was more ductile than of SM-CTT. Hence although the strength of BM-CTT was lower, the total energy absorption was as high as that of SM-CTT.

Figure 10 showed fracture parts of BM- and SM-CTT after impact tests. It has been reported in a previous study [15] that the fracture of CTT is divided into two patterns: fiber-dominated failure such as fiber breakage and matrix-dominated failure such as splitting of tapes and the shear fracture of interlayer resin between tapes. In addition, the more dominant the former fracture was, the greater strength of CTT become. As shown in Figure 10 (a), many tapes with original shape were left on the failure point of BM-CTT, and it is found that the many delamination of tapes' interlayer occurred. In contrast, many fiber breakages occurred in SM-CTT. This fracture mode transition seems to make the strength of SM-CTT greater.

Figure 8: Impact strength and total absorbed energy by three-point impact tests. Error bars show the standard deviation.

Figure 9: Fracture behavior of bulk molding- and sheet molding-CTT in three-point impact tests.

Figure 10: Fracture parts of bulk molding- and sheet molding-CTT specimens after three-point impact tests.

5 CONCLUSION

This study presented experimental work for tensile, flexural, and impact properties of CTT manufactured by different tape dispersion methods, in order to investigate the influence of tape dispersion process on the mechanical properties of CTT. One was bulk molding-CTT (BM-CTT), manufactured by compression molding of bulkily mixed tapes, and the other was sheet molding-CTT (SM-CTT), manufactured by compression molding of stacked CTT prepreg sheets with well dispersed tapes. Tapes in BM-CTT deformed and were oriented to out-of-plane direction, while most of tapes in SM-CTT were distributed in each plane parallel to the surface. There are two consistent trends through all experimental results, namely, great improvement of strength and decrease of scatter of mechanical properties from BM-CTT to SM-CTT. The observation of optical microscope suggested that dominant fracture mode changed from delamination of tapes' interlayer to fiber breakage, and it made the strength of SM-CTT greater. In addition, images of high speed camera characterized the fracture behavior in flexural and impact tests as fracture of BM-CTT showed more ductile than that of SM-CTT. The results of this study are quite useful to achieve CTT with higher strength and lower scatter of mechanical properties.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Part of this study has been conducted as the Japanese METI project "the Future Pioneering Projects / Innovative Structural Materials Project" since 2013fy. The authors would like to express sincere appreciation to the project members who have provided valuable information and useful discussion. In addition, the authors would like to thank Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture for supplying unidirectional prepreg sheet.

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